

PREVALENCE AND CONSEQUENCES OF INSECURITY AND INSURGENCY ON LIVESTOCK DATA: IMPLICATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION IN NORTH CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Prevalence and consequences of insecurity and insurgency on livestock data and its implications for improvement of livestock production in North Central, Nigeria were investigated. Data were collected from 3285 respondents spread across three States (Benue, Kwara and Niger) and the Federal Capital Territory using questionnaire and interview schedule. They were analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics (multiple regression and t-test). Findings show average length of residence, age, household size and livestock farming experience was 12 years, 35 years, 5 persons and 8 years respectively. Livestock farming was dominated by males (62.80%), who were married (62.60%) and with post-educational qualification (42.30%). Christianity dominated (78.62%) of the farming (51.70%). Poultry dominated (40,415) amongst other livestock kept by the farmers, while the total of the livestock was 141610 animals. Majority (83.84%) of the farmers acknowledged a very high effect of insecurity/insurgency on their livestock production. This is shown in difference of livestock performance which was respectively 10 and 5 before and after insecurity/insurgency. Several strategies like the control of banditry, conflicts and insurgency, provision of working capital and provision of infrastructural facilities were agreed to help improve livestock provision. Regression analysis result showed certain socio-economic characteristics like length of residence, gender, marital status, age, household size and farming experience had significant relationship on the number of livestock reared by the farmers ($R^2 = 62.80\%$) and that the difference in average number (5) was significant at 5% level. Results suggest that there is absolute need for the government of the federation to take up legit steps in combating the rate of insurgency in Nigeria generally and its northern part in particular.

Keywords: Insecurity/insurgency, livestock production, farmer's household, impact, performance,

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of insecurity in Nigeria has been on the increase since 1999 (Oduehie *et al.*, 2023). Insecurity has manifested in various forms like murder, rape, theft, car snatching, abduction, cultism, robbery of homes, offices, persons on transit, etc. (Abdullahi, 2019). Abdullahi (2019) opined that in whatever form insecurity occurs, it consequently leads to a threat on the society and as well causes a breakdown of societal law and order. One of the major consequences of insecurity is that it has resulted to the farming of only 32 million hectares out of the 92.4 million hectares of the country and for this reason, the country, Nigeria now lacks the capacity and

capability to cater for food and Insecurity in Nigeria has not helped matters sustainability of the livelihood of the in the area of livestock survey. This was

supported by Temesgen (2014) when he acknowledged, Nigeria has for some time now experienced serious occasions of internal conflict and insurgency and that these have caused a drastic reduction in agricultural productivity and investment. The situation has made farmers to have a shift in the interest of caring for themselves (which was supposed to be government's duty) which is time taking as against caring for the animals. By so doing, they seemed not have time to care for the animals or even have their interest. Better still, livestock population has been declining (2022) signing to fate

Musts of rise farmers live in a turbulence which is not profitable to the livestock and there they carry out their agricultural activities and that too has become an industry (Bourn, 2012).

livestock rearing and other income generating activities as their primary jobs or just to augment their primary jobs (Oduehie *et al.*, 2023). Oduehie *et al.* (2023) has stated that the activities in the livestock production and the availability of such income earners to farmers so as to assist them in general food security of the nation. Their activities have brought violence leading to deaths, kidnapping and abduction of the farmers and others within their reach both in their homes and farms. consequent

upon this situation, many farmers have The objectives of this study are therefore to ascertain the extent to which insecurity

experienced poor production leading to household food insecurity.

Livestock are those animals either kept by man or lives in man's environment and they include Chicken, Goat, Sheep, Cattle, Donkeys, Camels, Horses, Pigeon, Guinea Fowl, Ducks, Turkeys, Pigs, Dogs, Cats, Rabbits, Guinea Pigs, and Giant Rats (Bourn, 2012). Bourn (2012) stated that the animals are either domesticated and used as food or for other purposes, by man. Thakur (2012) described livestock as being very important because they significantly contribute to man's income, food, profit and livelihood. Although, the contribution of livestock to man's livelihood has declined due to insecurity (Temesgen, 2014).

Though, different researches have understudied the impact of insecurity on agricultural production, especially in northern Nigeria, there is still none in the recent past that has focused on impact of insecurity and insurgency on livestock data with a need to improving livestock production in North Central Nigeria. This creates a knowledge gap which this study intends to fill.

impacted on livestock production in the study area, analyse the rate of growth of livestock production amongst households before and after insurgency in the study area and identify strategies on how to improve on livestock production in the study area

production by households before insurgency is not significantly different from the rate after insurgency in the area.

The hypotheses were stated in their null forms are:

Hoi: Socio-economic characteristics of the livestock farmers is not significantly related to the number of livestock reared by the households in the area.

Hoi: The rate of growth of livestock

METHODOLOGY

Area of Study

The study was carried out in 3 States and the Federal Capital Territory (see Fig 1). They States were: Benue, Kwara and Niger State. and they are all in North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. They are described below as:

Figure 1: Shaded States show area of study:

Sampling technique and sample size the instruments were carried out by the In sampling the study's respondents, it researchers who were duly assisted by adopted multi-stage sampling technique trained enumerators. Residents were used as which started with the purposive selection enumerators so as to overcome issues of 3 States and the FCT from the North bothering on language difference and instill Central States in Nigeria. They include research confidence and legitimacy. Benue, Kwara, Niger States and FCT. This

was followed by the inclusion of all the **Validation of data collection/question** agricultural zones (3 per State) and the **instrument** Local Government Councils (LGCs) of Reliability of the instruments was FCT and this made the agricultural zones to ascertained through validity and reliability be 9 and the Council of the FCT (second approaches. Validity of the instrument was stage). In the third stage, 3 LGAs were carried out through presentation of the randomly selected from each of the question instrument to Experts in Agricultural zones, and that of FCT and this Agricultural Economics and Extension. The brought the number to 30 LGAs/LGCs. purpose was for them to go do and do the Fourth stage involved the random selection necessary corrections that will make the of 4 communities from each of the instrument address the study's objectives LGAs/LGCs, thus making it 120 and hypotheses. The reliability was carried villages/communities that were used for the out to determine internal consistency index study. In the fifth stage, a systematic random of the instrument after trial using test-re-test sampling technique was employed in technique. The technique involved the selecting 30 respondents from the administration of the instruments two villages/communities. Efforts were made to different times (but with 6 weeks in between avoid bias in the selection process and this first and second administration) to same set brought the number of respondents to 3600 of farmers. They were thereafter collated respondents. It was this number of and analysed. It yielded a Correlation respondents that were contacted and Coefficient ('r') of 0.716, which according administered with question instrument. to Okwuokenye, *et al.* (2023) implies a high From the returned question instruments, level of reliability of the instrument. 3285 (91.25%) of them that were correctly filled and fit for the study were used for **Analytical techniques of the study** analysis.

The analytical techniques used for data analysis include descriptive and inferential **Sources of data and data collection** statistics. Descriptive statistics employ **instruments** like frequency counts, frequency Data were sourced from both primary and tables, percentages, means and standard secondary sources. Primary data were deviations in its analysing process. The sourced from the respondents while data technique was used to analyse objectives of **the study** except for the 5 that identified, the Internet and so on constituted secondary the strategies on how to improve on **livestock** production) that applied the use of Primary data were collected with the use of a 4-point Likert scale. The 5-point Likert questionnaire and interview schedule. The scale ranges from "strongly agree" (coded questionnaires were used to source date 4), "agree" (coded 3), "disagree" (2) to from literate farmers while the interview "strongly disagree" (coded 1). The scale schedules were used to source information produced a weighted mean of 2.50 which from illiterate farmers. Important to was determined as follows: $\{4+3+2+1\} / 4 =$ mention, the administration and retrieval of 2.50.

Likert-scale was used to assert if the respondents agreed (if mean ≥ 2.50) to the strategy under consideration or not (if mean < 2.50). On the other hand, where weighted mean is less than 2.50, it implies that respondents did not agree that the strategy or factor under consideration is capable of improving livestock production. Inferential statistics involved multiple regression analysis and t-test statistics. Multiple regression was used to determine the relationship of livestock farmers socio-economic characteristics and the extent to which insecurity has affected the production level. The regression equation is specified as:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_nX_n \dots \dots \dots \text{(eq.1)}$$

- Y = Production level (High = 1; low = 0)
- X₁ = Gender (dummy: male = 1; female = 0)
- X₂ = Age (years)
- X₃ = Education (pri. educ. = 1, sec. educ. = 2 and tertiary educ. = 3)
- X₄ = Marital status (single = 1, married = 2, divorced = 3, widow (ep) = 4)
- X₅ = Livestock rearing experience (years)
- X₆ = Household size (number of persons living and feeding together)
- X₇ = Length of residence (years)
- X₈ = Religious affiliation (Christian = 1; Muslim = 2; Traditionalist = 3)

- S₁ = standard deviation for effect before insurgency; S₂ = standard deviation for after insurgency
- S₂₁ = variance of the effect before insurgency; S₂² = variance of the effect after insurgency
- n₁ = size of the first group; n₂ = size of the second group; $\sqrt{\quad}$ = square root

Decision rule for t₁- statistics If the t calculated is greater than the t-tabulated, it implies rejecting the null and accept the alternative hypothesis. If on the other hand, t-tabulated is greater than t-calculated, we accept the null and reject the alternative hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
Socio-economic characteristics of the

respondents of the study. n = 3285

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 2. The results of household size (number of persons living and feeding together) in the study area is dominated (52.65%) by about 10 – 14 years and the average period of residence (years) was 12 years.

The study area is dominated (52.65%) by about 10 – 14 years and the average period of residence (years) was 12 years.

The result implies that the farmers have the experience of how to rear and cater for livestock in the area. Rearing of livestock in the area is skewed towards males (62.80%) and this may be adduced to either the tedious nature of work involved in rearing livestock or the resident’s religious belief that women should stay in “purdah”. Respondents’ marital status revealed that majority (62.6%) of them are married and this implies that they are responsible since they have people to provide with economic needs. The respondents have an average age of 35 years with majority (42.28 %) of them

T – test was used to determine the effect of insurgency on livestock production. This was carried out in a before and after basis. The formula for t- test is as shown below: Where:

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{S_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

- \bar{X}_1 = the mean for effect before insurgency
- \bar{X}_2 = the mean for effect after insurgency

belonging to between 26 – 34 years. With and embrace new technologies. A larger this age range, they are described as young, fraction (78.62%) of the respondents were in their active age group and can withstand of the Christian religion. The others were the rigors of the farming activities. Results respectively of the practice of Islamic on age, gender and marital status are in religion (11.97%), Traditionalist (5.85%) consonance with Musab & Otovwe (2021), and other religions (3.56%). They also had who stated that majority of livestock an average household size of 5 persons with farmers to be between 20 – 30 years, the modal (58.26%) having between 4 – 6 dominated by males and are married. persons as their household size. The result

The educational level of the respondents implies that the farmers have large revealed that most (41.30%) of them had household size and this can be used as post-secondary qualification. Close to this source of farm labour thus helping to save was about 37.10% of them that had farm income. This result is consistent with secondary school qualification. About 16% Okwuokenye *et al.* (2023) who observed in and 5.70% respectively had primary and no similar area, the dominance of farmers with formal education. The result shows that post-secondary qualification who are of respondents had one form of education or Christian religious practice and have large the other implying that they can appreciate household size.

Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Socio-economic variables Categories		Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Length of residence (range)	<5 5-9 10-14 15-19	219	6.67	
	>=20 Female	742	22.5	
Sex	Male	172	9	
	Single	9	52.6	
	Married	375	5	12
	Divorced	219	11.4	
	Widow	122	2	
Marital status	Widower	122	2	
	<25	3	6.67	
	26-34	206	37.2	
	35-44	2	0	
	45-54	707	62.8	
Age range (years)	>=55	205	0	
	No formal education	5	21.5	
	Primary educ.	201	0	
	Secondary educ.	252	62.6	
	Post-secondary educ.	70	0	
Education	411	6.10	35	
	138	7.70		
	8	2.10		
	864	12.5		
	573	2		
Religion	Traditional	573	2	
	Others	47	42.2	
	1-3	186	8	
	4-6	524	26.3	
	7-9	121	2	
Household size range	10-12	8	17.4	
	13 & above	135	5	
	Part-time	7	1.43	
	Full-time	258	5.70	
	<5	2	16.0	
Farming status	5-9	393	0	5
	10-14	192	37.1	
	15-19	117	0	
Farming experience range (years)	>=20	662	41.3	
	191	0		
	4	78.6		
	662	2		
	37	11.9	8	
<i>Source: Field survey, 2023</i>	10	7		
	169	5.85		
	7	3.56		
	158	20.1		
	8	5		
	304	58.2		
	222	6		
	9	20.1		
	614	5		
	76	1.13		
62	0.30			
	51.7			
	0			
	48.2			

Results also revealed that majority of the various livestock reared by the respondents in part-time farming while the others (48.30%) were into full-time farming. Dominance of Horses, Camels, Dogs, Cats, Donkeys, Rabbits and other animals. The number of animals being reared by the farmers include: Cattle (14,915), Goats (15,830), Sheep (7,230), Pigs (21,393), Poultry (40,415), Other birds (9,675), Horses (1,505), Camels (390), Dogs (8,650), Cats (4,185), Donkeys (1,735), Rabbits (3,750) and other animals (8,695). In all it could be deduced from calculation that the total number of livestock in the area of study was 141,610. Though personal communication, the farmers noted that the average period they have spent in their livestock farming, with majority (67.90%) what they had as at the time of this study if not the so much that had been lost to insurgency. About 9.30% and 22.90% respectively had less than 5 years and more than 9 years farming experience. Impliedly, majority of animals shows that Poultry had the highest (mean = 19) and the may be ascribed to the fact that poultry farming can be carried out with any little sum of money and its consumption and use is not restrained by any tradition, culture or religion. The respondents have many years of livestock rearing experience and that is expected to translate to higher returns for livestock production. This study agrees with Ishaya *et al.* (2018) who observed similar number of poultry reared is respectively experience of livestock farmers and that followed by Pigs (mean = 13), Other birds (mean = 11), Sheep (mean = 10), Cattle (mean = 7), Rabbit (mean = 7), Goats (mean = 6), Camels (mean = 6), Donkeys (mean = 6), Other animals (mean = 6), Horses (mean = 5), Dogs (mean = 5) and Cats (mean = 5). The result implies that there are various livestock in the area. Through personal communication, some of the respondents noted that it is not all the animals that are eaten by them. Rather animals like Dogs are kept for security purposes and alertness while Cats are kept either as pets or for the control of rodents that may want to destroy their goods.

Number of commercially managed livestock holdings

The number and types of the different animals reared by the livestock farmers in the study area is shown in Table 3. In determining the number of the animals reared, the mid-class of each of the different animals was first taken and this was then used to multiple the corresponding frequency for each of the livestock reared.

Table 3: Size of commercially managed livestock holdings

Livestock	<=10		10-19		20-29		30-39		>=40		Mean
	Freq	F.X5 %	Freq	F.X15 %	Freq	F.X25 %	Freq	F.X35 %	Freq	F.X45 %	
Cattle	1814	9070 55.22	118	1770 3.59	121	3025 3.68	21	735 0.64	7	315 0.2	14915 7
Goats	2247	11235 68.40	209	3135 6.36	9	225 0.27	1	35 0.03	28	1260 0.8	15890 6
Sheep	488	2440 14.86	232	3480 7.06	2	50 0.06	0	0 0.00	28	1260 0.8	7230 10
Pigs	922	4610 28.08	609	9135 18.5	4	394 9850 12.0	28	980 0.85	0	0 0.0	24575 13
Poultry	643	3215 19.58	551	8265 16.7	8	560 14000 17.0	275	9625 8.37	1	5310 3.5	40415 19
Other birds	623	3115 18.96	128	1920 3.90	125	3125 3.81	42	1470 1.28	8	45 0.0	9675 11
Horses	292	1460 8.89	3	45 0.09	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	1505 5
Camels	67	335 2.04	2	30 0.06	1	25 0.03	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	390 6
Dogs	1598	7990 48.65	44	660 1.34	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	8650 5
Cats	730	3650 22.42	34	510 1.04	1	25 0.03	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	4185 5
Donkeys	251	1255 7.64	32	480 0.97	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	1735 6
Rabbits	450	2250 13.70	96	1440 2.92	1	25 0.03	1	35 0.03	0	0 0.0	3750 7
Other animals	1372	6860 41.77	74	1110 2.25	29	725 0.88	0	0 0.00	0	0 0.0	8695 6
Total	11497	57485		31980		31075		12880		8190	141610

Source: Field survey, 2023

Extent to which insecurity/insurgency impacted on livestock production

Table 4 shows extent to which insecurity has impacted on livestock production in the area. The results revealed that majority (83.84%) of the respondents indicated that insecurity/insurgency has negatively impacted on their livestock production to a very high extent. The others, notably 12.42%, 3.47% and 0.27% respectively

indicated that insecurity/insurgency has similar effect on their livestock farming activities to a high extent, average extent and low extent. This result is corroborated by findings of Yau *et al.* (2021) which indicated that incidence of insurgency has resulted to making livestock farming which include cows, goats, cattle, and birds to be quite scarce, and this has translated to hike in the prices of these products.

Table 4: Extent to which insecurity/insurgency impacted on livestock production

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Extent of insecurity/insurgency impact on livestock production	Low extent	9 114 408	0.27	3.47 12.42
	Average extent	2754 3285	83.84	100.00
	High extent			
	Very high extent			
	Total			Very high

Source: Field survey, 2023

Rate of growth of livestock amongst households before and after insurgency

The results on rate of growth of livestock performance amongst the farmers before and after insecurity/insurgency is shown in Table 5. The results imply that (52.30%) of the livestock farmers had their livestock increase at a rate of between 10 – 14 animals per annum before the rate of growth of insecurity/insurgency. It was however observed that the rate of growth of livestock performance after insecurity/insurgency, the number of livestock produced by the farmers and this is (60.06%) of the livestock farmers decreased production and food insecurity status of the farmers in particular and livestock production in general. This finding and assertion

Table 5: Rate of growth of livestock amongst households before and after Adola and Oboshi (2015) who reported that farm households have experienced food insecurity and poor production since the escalation of *Boko Haram* in 2013.

insecurity/insurgency				
Variables	Category(per annual basis)	Freq	%	Mean
Livestock performance before insecurity	Increase by <5 animals	177	5.39	
	Increased by 5-9 animals	1118	34.03	
	Increased by 10-14 animals	1718	52.30	
	Increased by 15-19 animals	272	8.28	
	Total Increase by <5 animals	3285	100.00	10
Livestock performance after insecurity	Increased by 5-9 animals	1973	60.06	
	Increased by 10-14 animals	1100	33.49	
	Total	212	6.45	
		3285	100.00	5

Source: Field survey, 2023

Strategies on how to improve on livestock production The strategies on how to improve on livestock production in the area of insecurity/insurgency is shown in Table 6. Results revealed that there are many strategies or measures or ways the farmers agreed can help to improve on animal production. First, second, third and fourth amongst them is the control of banditry, conflict and insurgency (mean = 4.00), provision of working capital (mean = 3.64), provision of infrastructural facilities (mean = 3.52) and provision of government assistance (mean = 3.38). Other agreed strategies or measures to achieve increased livestock production were control of pest and diseases (mean = 3.08), provision

of farm inputs (mean = 3.06), application of improved technology in the production process (mean = 2.98), training of farmers on improved livestock farming technology (mean 2.73) and farmers encouragement on integrated livestock farming system into cropping systems (mean = 2.61).

The results on provision of working capital of the farmers and provision of adequate and appropriate inputs to farmers were in collaboration with the findings of Offor *et al.* (2018); Jare and Bunu (2021) as their findings respectively suggested that employing the strategies of organizing the farmers into cooperatives and as well providing them with loans will do them well in improving their production level. Results on control of

insurgency and provision of government encouraging farmers into engaging in assistance were supported by the findings of integrated crop farming systems were Ishaya *et al.* (2018) which stated that agreed by findings of Fasoyiro and Taiwo government should do well to restoring (2012) as strategies that can boost peace and security in insurgency affected agricultural production of the farmers. areas in order to improve farmers Findings of Offor *et al.* (2018) on control agricultural production. Also, provision of of pest and diseases agreed with the result infrastructural facilities will also help to of the study. They stated that such control improve production capabilities of the is capable of increasing the number of farmers in the areas of insurgency. Results agricultural products that will be available showing development and use of to the people. appropriate technology and

Table 6: Strategies on how to improve on livestock production

Variables	SD		D		Total		SA		
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	Mean	SD	%	
- Control of banditry, conflicts and insurgency	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	3285	100.00	4.00* 0.0
- Provision of working capital	0	0.00	1	0.03	1185	36.07	2099	63.90	3.64* 0.5
- Provision infrastructural facilities	0	0.00	366	11.14	832	25.33	2087	63.53	3.52* 0.7
- Provision of government assistance	0	0.00	366	11.14	1300	39.57	1619	49.28	3.38* 0.7
- Control of Pest and diseases	0	0.00	227	6.91	2561	78.01	495	15.08	3.08* 0.5
- Provision of farm input	62	1.89	145	4.41	2621	79.79	457	13.91	3.06* 0.5
- Application of improved technology in the production process	0	0.00	525	15.98	2306	70.20	454	13.82	2.98* 0.5
- Training of farmers on improved livestock farming technology	0	0.00	432	13.15	2427	73.88	426	12.97	2.73* 0.6
- Farmers encouragement on integrated livestock farming system into cropping systems	0	0.00	432	13.15	2239	68.16	614	18.69	2.61* 0.6
- Provision of manpower	2097	63.84	1125	34.25	63	1.92	0	0.00	1.38 0.5
- Provision of equipment	2633	80.15	652	19.85	0	0.00	0	0.00	1.20 0.4
- Use of the local people/residents in farming operation	2844	86.58	244	7.43	165	5.02	32	0.97	1.20 0.6

Source: Field survey, 2023

*Agreed factor (mean = 2.50)

Relationship between respondents' socio-economic characteristics and the

number of livestock reared by their households at 5% level

The relationship between respondents' of probability to the number of livestock socio-economic characteristics and the reared by the farmers. The result shows that number of livestock reared by their married farmers dominated (62.60%) households is analysed using Multiple livestock farming in the study area.

regression analysis and the results is shown. Impliedly, a unit increase in the number of was 0.6833 and it implies that the while holding every other factor constant

in Table 7. The coefficient of adjusted R² married people in the farming of livestock independent variables (socio-economic led to 0.625 unit increase in the number of characteristics) accounted for about 62.12% livestock reared by the farmers. The result variation in the dependent variable (number corroborates that of Mohammed *et al.*

of livestock reared). The regression result (2015) who was of the opinion that marriage shows that variables like length of is a sacred institution, cherished among the residence, gender, marital status, age, people and compels heads of households to household size and farming experience produce more so as to be able to cater for were found to have significant relationship their responsibilities advanced from family on the number of livestock reared by the circles. The coefficient of age was farmers. The results are further explained statistically significant at 1% level of

significance but inversely related to the

number of livestock reared by the farmers. Age and its terms indicates that a unit increase in the age farmers will result to a decrease in the number of livestock reared by 2.449 unit. By implication, as age of the farmers increase, number of livestock reared will begin to decrease, all things being equal. The result indicates that older farmers may show reluctance to adopt new technologies in the field of production process may become more labourious for them to cope with, hence a reduction in the number of livestock produced. The result is in conformity with the observation of Olorung *et al.* (2018).

other factors constant led to increase in the number of livestock reared by 3.671 unit.

Having spent a greater number of years in a particular community/village will afford the farmers a background knowledge or information on how to avoid errors and apply good management skills or practices on how to develop themselves on livestock farming. The coefficient of gender was positively signed and significant at the 5% level of probability. This shows that men

The coefficient of household size was dominated (62.80%) livestock production positive and significantly related to the in the study area. The result indicates a unit number of livestock reared by the increase in the number of men involved in respondents. This implies that an increase by one person in household size, increases

livestock production, holding every other factor constant led to increase in the number the number of livestock reared by 1.586

unit of livestock reared by the individual. This result

agreed with findings of Melissa *et al.* (2016) household could be a source of farm labour who found the involvement of more men in to the farming activities and so money livestock production and that the labour can

them be saved. This result is at variance with livestock reared in the study area. Farming that of Offor *et al.* (2018) who recorded experience of livestock will necessarily negative relationship between labour and provide the farmers with the ability to income earned from production of small manage farm resources effectively and ruminants. Livestock farming experience of perhaps translate to having more livestock the respondents was positive ($b = 2.440$) and produced in the farmers' farm. This result is significant at 5% level of probability similar to findings of Ishaya *et al.* (2018) indicating a direct relationship with the who stated that having more experience in number of livestock reared by the farmers. cattle rearing will lead to efficient The result implies that a unit increase in management of resources and higher returns farming experience of livestock will from the farming activities. increase the efficiency in the number of

Table 7: Relationship of respondents' socio-economic characteristics and the number of livestock reared by their households

Socio-economic variables	Beta Coefficients	Standarderror (SE)	t-value
(Constant)	0.995	0.398	8.42
Length of residence (year)	3.671	0.099	2.925**
Gender	0.472	0.143	1.550*
Marital status	0.625	0.051	1.259*
Age (years)	-2.449	-0.094	3.411**
Education	0.812	0.616	1.001
Household size (no.)	1.586	0.004	1.402*
Farmingstatus	0.337	0.325	0.227
Farmingexperience (years)	2.440	1.019	2.306*
Religiousaffiliation	0.301	0.200	1.225

$R^2 = 68.33$; Adjusted $R^2 = 62.12$; $p=0.05$); Dependent Variable: Number of livestock reared by households

*Significant at 5% level; **significant at 1% level

Effect of insecurity/insurgency on livestock production

The results (Table8)showedthatthe average numberofanimalskeptbythe livestockfarmersbefore insecurity/insurgencywas10.Whileafter insurgency,itdroppedto5animals.The results showedthatthenumberwashigher than whatitwasafterinsurgency.The differenceinthenumberbeforeandafter insurgencywas5livestock.The difference in numberwassignificantsincethe calculatedtvalue(21.423)wasgreaterthan

the tabulated t value at the 5% level (1.645). Based on this the alternative hypothesis was accepted against the null and it states that, the rate of growth of livestock production by households before insurgency is significantly different from the rate after insurgency in the area. The result suggests that incidence of insecurity/insurgency has negatively affected the production of livestock in the area. This finding is supported by results of Awodola and Oboshi (2015) who reported a drop in food production due to insecurity. Hassan and Lawal (2023) also share same view as they

noted that insecurity/insurgency has resulted to reduction of investments in animal production which has consequently led to negative impacts on supply chains and animals' productivity losses

Table 8: Effect of insecurity/insurgency on livestock production (t-test)

Livestockperformance	No.	Income (₦)		t	Decision
		Meanof animals	Difference		
Livestockperformance beforeinsecurity	3285	10	5	21.423*	Significant
Livestockperformance after insecurity	3285	5			

*Significant at the 5% level (critical t- value = 1.645)

Conclusion and Recommendations

From results of the study, it could be concluded that poultry was the commonest and larger number of livestock produced/reared in high commercial quantity by the farmers and this may be linked to it being free from religious, traditional and customarily biases. It was also found that insurgency has really and negatively affected the production of livestock to a very high extent and such is responsible for the low number of livestock available in the area.

The effect of insurgency is manifested in the difference in the average level of performance or number of livestock produced which was respectively 10 and 5 before and after incidence of insecurity/insurgency. The number of livestock produced in the area can be increased if several strategies like banditry, conflicts andinsurgency,provision of working capital, provision infrastructural facilities and provision of government assistance, amongst others can be adopted by the people and the government of the affected States and the country in general. Socio-economic characteristics length of residence, gender, marital status, age, household size and farming experience were found to have relationship with number of livestock reared by the farmers.

The study therefore recommended that:

- There is absolute need for the government of the federation to take up legit steps in combating the rate of insurgency in the country in general and the northern area of the country in particular. Doing this will help create a peaceful environment for the farmers to continue and increase in their farming activities and output.
- There is also the need for the farmers to be organized into small cooperative societies where they can contribute their meagre resources and enjoy the possibility of carrying loans for larger scale production.
- The farmers also need to be assisted by the government in the area of making improved farm inputs and infrastructural facilities available to the farmers. It is expected that such facilities will go a long way in encouraging the farmers into rearing more animals for consumption and other uses, and;
- The inputs should be made available at subsidized rate to the farmers for use in their farming activities as well making extension services available to the people for better knowledge and improved productivity.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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